

An overview of the possibilities, current status, and limitations of battery technologies to electrify aviation

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Abstract:

This work aims to discuss the feasibility of including battery technologies to electrify aviation, highlighting their great potential, but also outlining some of the main technological challenges that will be faced in the coming years. The work is framed within the EFACA (Environmentally Friendly Aviation for All Classes of Aircraft) project, a project funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe Programme, which focusses on the analysis and development of new technologies to make aviation more sustainable.

The first step in determining which applications of battery technology are most suitable for each type of aircraft is to have an overview of these technologies; understand the main challenges when including batteries in aviation (battery performance, safety issues, problems in battery manufacturing, and disposal); and study the performance metrics characteristic of each type and establish a battery classification. From batteries, based on such important characteristics as their specific energy requirements or operating profiles, it is possible to define aircraft types according to the different applications and extend the study to aircraft classes.

This work presents a summary of all the aforementioned topics, from a first presentation of batteries, their possibilities in the electrification of aviation and the main technological challenges, to a classification of batteries according to their performance metrics. This is followed by a characterisation of which types of aircraft could use these technologies and what technological developments should be achieved to continue progress towards a cleaner aviation.

Keywords: environmentally friendly aviation, aircraft classes, battery technology in aviation, electrification of aviation

1. Aviation Electrification: A Path to Sustainable Air Travel.

The concept of aviation electrification is a game changer for the aviation industry as it aims to replace fossil fuel-based propulsion systems with electric powertrains in aircraft. The goal is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, decrease

dependence on fossil fuels, and mitigate the environmental impact of air travel. Battery technologies are a crucial component of aviation electrification as they provide a sustainable and clean energy source for electric aircraft.

The benefits of electrification are numerous, including zero direct emissions during flight, quieter propulsion systems that reduce noise pollution, and higher energy conversion efficiencies that can lead to potential fuel savings and increased operational efficiency.

Governments, research institutions, aircraft manufacturers, and airlines are actively pursuing the development and deployment of electric aircraft to drive the electrification movement. Key initiatives such as the European Union's Clean Sky program and NASA's X-57 Maxwell aircraft project are driving research and development efforts to accelerate the integration of battery technologies into aviation.

Battery technologies are integral to the electrification of aviation, providing energy storage that powers electric aircraft. The adoption of battery technologies in aviation electrification is driven by advancements in energy storage, power electronics, and electric motor technologies.

The role of battery technologies in aviation electrification can be summarized as powering electric propulsion systems, enabling energy storage, supporting hybrid-electric configurations, enhancing safety and redundancy, and facilitating ground operations.

They provide the high power output necessary for takeoff, climb, and cruise phases of flight, allowing electric aircraft to achieve sufficient thrust and propulsion. Batteries also allow for efficient capture and storage of energy during ground charging or regenerative braking, and release it during flight operations to power the aircraft.

In hybrid-electric aircraft configurations, batteries work with other power sources such as fuel cells or gas turbines to provide additional power during high-demand phases of flight, while the primary power source handles sustained cruise phases. Furthermore, batteries play a crucial role in enhancing safety and redundancy by providing multiple power sources for critical systems. They also facilitate ground operations by providing power for aircraft ground support equipment, such as electric tugs, charging infrastructure, and maintenance tools.

The following sections will explore the possibilities, current status, and limitations of various battery technologies in aviation electrification.

2. Aviation Battery Technologies: What They Need to Succeed.

Aviation battery technologies serve a vital role in ensuring safe and efficient aviation operations. To guarantee the success of these technologies, several key requirements must be met. These include:

- **Energy Density:** Refers to the amount of energy stored in a battery per unit mass or volume. The ability to store ample energy in a confined area is crucial for

aviation battery technologies. A high energy density enables electric aircraft to fly long distances while still carrying a full payload.

Power Density: Represents the rate at which a battery can deliver energy. It refers to a battery's capacity to deliver high power output rapidly. Higher power density is crucial for meeting quick energy demands in aviation, such as takeoff or rapid acceleration.

- **Cycle Life:** Indicates the number of charge-discharge cycles a battery can undergo before its capacity degrades significantly. Higher cycle life means longer-lasting batteries, reducing the need for frequent replacements. Aviation batteries are expected to last a long time, withstanding numerous charge-discharge cycles without significant performance degradation.
- **Safety:** Batteries should be designed with robust safety features to prevent thermal runaway, overheating, or fire hazards. Advanced battery management systems are employed to monitor and control battery conditions.
- **Weight and Space Constraints.** Battery technologies must be lightweight while still maintaining high energy density to minimize overall weight and maximize payload capacity. Additionally, space constraints in aircraft require battery packs to be compact and efficient.
- **Temperature tolerance:** Electric aircraft operate in a variety of temperature conditions, high altitudes and extreme weather, and battery technologies must have good temperature tolerance and provide optimal performance over a wide temperature range without compromising safety or efficiency.
- **Fast-charge capability:** Battery technologies for aviation should support fast charging without compromising safety or durability, so that aircraft can be quickly returned to service.
- **Environmental sustainability:** This includes aspects such as the use of non-toxic materials, recyclability, and compliance with environmental regulations.

Meeting these key requirements is critical to the successful integration of battery technologies into aviation and ensures that electric aircraft can operate reliably, efficiently, and safely.

3. Pay attention to performances.

The electrification of airplanes still faces a number of technological obstacles, one of which is the performance criteria needed for batteries. It is difficult to find a complete set of performance parameters needed for next-generation batteries to electrify commercial airplanes. In terms of performance indicators, Carnegie Mellon University research has produced one of the most pertinent and thorough works.

Fig. 1 illustrates a characteristic mission for analysing the performance needs. An airplane takes off from the ground, soars to its cruising altitude, flies there, then returns by descending to a level that is close to ground level and landing. Emergency reserve energy (ERE) is defined as an additional 30% battery state of charge (SoC) for unforeseen events like diversions or failed landings.

Fig.1. Oversimplified mission profile with flight phases and key time instants indicated. Full flight profile, including holding and diversion. (Bærheim, Lamb, Noland, & Burheim, 2023)

For the sake of performance analysis in this paper commercial aircraft is divided into three categories: regional, narrow-body, and wide-body. Wide-body aircraft carry high passenger loads (200–400) and travel on much longer journeys (>2000 nmi), whereas regional aircraft normally fly short missions of about 500 nmi and carry low passenger loads (30–75). Between the two are narrow-body aircraft, which have 1000 nautical mile flight ranges and can carry medium passenger loads.

The empty weight fraction, wing aspect ratio, wing loading, drag coefficient, and mechanical efficiency data from more than two dozen commercial aircraft types, energy density needs for hypothetical airplanes were calculated (fig.2).

Fig.2. Parameters used to estimate specific power and energy of a prospective electric aircraft for various classes of commercial aircraft.

With such characteristics, Montecarlo simulations of the predetermined missions for each class of aircraft revealed that the typical regional aircraft would require 600Wh/kg of battery density, narrow bodies 820Wh/kg, and widebodies a whopping 1,280Wh/kg. according to fig. 3.

Fig.3. Histograms of specific energy for regional, narrow-body, and wide-body electric aircraft.

The data in fig.3 have means for each segment of aircraft of about 600, 820, and 1280 Wh/kg-pack, with standard deviations of 61, 81, and 105 Wh/kg-pack, respectively. The trend of increasing specific energy with aircraft size is not due primarily to the larger size of these aircraft but rather to the longer-range use cases for which they are employed.

For regional aircraft, the average range is currently obtained at a pack-level specific energy of about 2000 Wh/kg, while the average passenger miles are currently achieved at a pack-level specific energy of roughly 1400 Wh/kg. A realistic all-electric regional aircraft has to have a threshold of 500 Wh/kg to cover around 25% of the average range at this time. For narrow-body and wide-body, the threshold is around 800 and 1700 Wh/kg, respectively. At threshold-specific energies, only 12 and 16% of the current average range are reached, respectively. Only 19 and 16% of the present average range and passenger miles can be reached by electric wide-body aircraft at the greatest pack-level specific energy taken into account, which is 2000 Wh/kg. Regional aircraft have substantially greater range and passenger kilometers than the current average at 2000 Wh/kg.

4. Battery electrochemical cell technologies for aviation electrification

There could be different approaches for grouping and characterising batteries. At a very high-level approach batteries are commonly classified into two main groups: primary and secondary batteries. Primary batteries are non-rechargeable and once they are depleted, they are disposed of. Examples like alkaline batteries have had a broad range of uses, but non rechargeability discards them as an option in the objectives for a cleaner aviation. On the other hand, batteries with the ability to be recharged are commonly known as secondary batteries. This paper is only concerned with secondary type batteries as primary ones are not suitable to aviation application. Within the broad secondary category this chapter follows the scheme depicted below, which mainly considers the nature of the cell chemistry.

- **Lithium-ion batteries.** With higher energy density these are the most popular batteries in aviation in present day. Even though they exhibit higher energy densities than the previous category, they do still present limitations in relation to the energy density ceiling that can be achieved and safety issues.
- **Beyond lithium-ion batteries.** This category of batteries, which is being actively researched nowadays, assemblies those that search for even higher energy density by exploiting the potential of using alternative electrodes. Two different possible types of electrodes are considered in the pursue of designing high energy batteries, insertion electrodes and conversion electrodes, both leading to a subclassification of beyond lithium-ion batteries.
 - **Beyond lithium-ion batteries with insertion electrodes.** These involve the insertion or removal of an active ion into the inactive host framework, with no change in its structure. As alternative that can replace lithium ion in insertion electrode redox reactions, other active ions under study currently include aluminium, sodium, manganese, zinc, etc
 - **Beyond lithium-ion batteries with conversion electrodes.** These implies bond breakage and important structural changes in the electrodes during the redox reaction. These types of batteries imply the use of conversion electrodes (metal anode, mainly lithium, but also sodium, zinc, aluminium or manganese), combined with sulphur or oxygen in the cathode.
- **All solid-state batteries.** It is possible also to pursue higher energy densities by considering alternative electrolytes. Batteries can use a liquid electrolyte (either non-aqueous, i.e. organic, or aqueous) or they can use a solid-state electrolyte. All solid-state batteries are characterised by a solid-state electrolyte. In this battery type, the anode is metal, usually lithium, and the cathode can be either one of the ones used in lithium ion batteries, sulphur like in Li-S, (this last combination known as LiS-ASSB Lithium Sulphur all solid state battery, one of the most promising cell batteries under study today), or can also be O₂ (like in metal-air batteries solid state batteries)
- **Flow batteries.** These are a type of electrochemical cells in which the liquid electrolyte is stored in external tanks. This allows a separation of the energy and the power that the battery can supply, with the energy storage capability being related to the storage tanks and the power capability being related to the cell stack.

Table 1 summaries the possibilities, current status and limitations of the most relevant of the previous categories.

Trough the following sections state of the art, potential and limitations of these categories of batteries are comparatively studied. We also examine the potential of the various battery chemistries to meet the previously mentioned targets after identifying the energy and power needs, and other key requirements.

Table 1: Possibilities, current status and limitations of the most relevant batteries categories.

Insertion electrodes			
	Possibilities	Current Status	Limitations
Sodium-ion (Na-ion)	Higher abundance of sodium resources. Potentially more cost-effective than Li-ion batteries. Could provide high energy density, longer lifespan, and improved safety features for aviation applications.	Research and development to improve the performance and stability of Na-ion batteries. Not yet commercially available for aviation applications. Further optimization is required to achieve the desired energy density and cycle life.	Lower energy density compared to Li-ion batteries. Larger size of sodium ions. Potential degradation of the anode during cycling
Aluminum-ion (Al-ion)	Potential for high energy density, improved safety, and lower cost compared to Li-ion batteries. Aluminum is abundant and widely available, making it an attractive alternative for aviation applications.	Still in the early stages of development and face several technical challenges. Researcher on improving the stability and capacity, as well as addressing issues related to dendrite formation, which can affect their long-term performance.	Lack of suitable electrolyte materials that can efficiently transport aluminum ions. Developing electrolytes with high ionic conductivity and stability remains a significant challenge.
Magnesium-ion (Mg-ion)	Magnesium is abundant and offers a higher energy density than lithium. Potential to provide improved energy storage capacity, increased safety, and reduced cost compared to Li-ion batteries.	Still in the early stages of development. Researchers are exploring electrode materials and electrolytes that can enable reversible magnesium-ion intercalation and improve the overall performance of Mg-ion batteries.	Lack of suitable electrolytes and electrode materials that can efficiently accommodate magnesium ions. Development of high-performance cathode materials that can reversibly intercalate magnesium ions.
Zinc-ion (Zn-ion)	Zinc is abundant, low-cost, and offers good energy storage capabilities. Potentially provide high energy density, improved safety, and lower cost compared to Li-ion batteries.	Still in the early stages of development. Focus on improving the cycling stability, energy density, and safety of Zn-ion batteries to make them suitable for aviation and other applications.	Zinc dendrite formatio affect their long-term cycling stability. Developing suitable electrolytes and addressing dendrite formation.
Conversion electrodes			
	Possibilities	Current Status	Limitations
Lithium-Air (Li-Air)	Extremely high theoretical energy density, potentially surpassing other battery technologies. Reduce the overall weight of the battery. The high energy density could significantly extend the range of electric aircraft.	Still in the early stages of development and face significant technical challenges. Reaction between lithium and oxygen needs to be optimized to achieve practical cycling stability and efficiency. Development of suitable cathode materials and electrolytes remains a key focus of research.	Formation of insoluble lithium peroxide during discharge, which hampers the reversibility of the reaction and leads to capacity loss. Management of moisture and carbon dioxide in the air, electrode and electrolyte stability, and the prevention of lithium dendrite formation.

Lithium-Selenium (Li-Se)	Potential for high energy density and improved safety compared to Li-S batteries. Reversible redox reactions and stable cycling performance. Viable option for aviation applications by addressing some of the challenges faced by other conversion-based battery systems.	Still in the early stages, and significant progress is required to optimize their performance and address technical challenges. The development of stable electrode materials and electrolytes is a focus of ongoing research.	Volume expansion and contraction of selenium during cycling, which can cause mechanical stress on the electrode and lead to capacity decay. Reaction by products and the need for efficient charge transfer pathways remain areas of exploration.
	Possibilities	Current Status	Limitations
Flow batteries	Potentially provide higher energy storage capacities compared to conventional batteries, crucial for long-duration flights or high power demands. Recharged quickly by replacing or replenishing the electrolyte, enabling faster turnaround times during ground operations. Flexibility in sizing and scalability. Safer than some conventional batteries, such as lithium-ion batteries, as they don't have the risk of thermal runaway or catastrophic failures.	Still in the early stages of research and development. Some proof-of-concept demonstrations have shown promising results in terms of flow battery technology's potential for aviation applications, but practical implementation is yet to be realized. Currently, flow batteries are used in stationary energy storage applications, such as grid-scale energy storage or renewable energy integration, rather than aviation.	Lower energy density compared to conventional batteries, meaning they store less energy per unit mass or volume. Lower power density compared to some conventional battery technologies. Larger size and weight of flow battery systems. Would require designing compatible infrastructure, integrating them into the aircraft's power management system, and addressing the associated logistical challenges.

4.1. Main parameters and relevant characteristics of different battery types for aviation applications

Table 2 presents a comparative table outline of the main parameters and relevant characteristics of previous battery types. The table provides a general comparison of the characteristics and parameters for each battery type. The actual values may vary depending on the specific battery chemistry, design, and technological advancements. Characteristics used in the comparison are: Energy Density, Power Density, Cycle Life, Safety, Size & Weight, Charging Time and Cost.

Table 2: Comparative outline of the main parameters and relevant characteristics of previous battery types.

Battery Type	Energy Density	Power Density	Cycle Life	Safety	Size & Weight	Charging Time	Cost
Flow Batteries	Medium to High	Low to Medium	High	Safe	Large & Heavy	Moderate	Moderate to High
All-Solid Batteries	High	Medium	High	High safety	Compact	Moderate	High
Beyond Lithium-ion (Insertion)	Medium to High	High	High	Moderate safety	Compact	Moderate	High
Beyond Lithium-ion (Conversion)	High	Medium	Moderate to High	Moderate safety	Compact	Moderate	High
Lithium-ion Batteries	High	High	High	Moderate safety	Compact	Moderate	Moderate

4.2. Performance factors

Table 2 summarises of the potential magnitude of energy density and power density for the mentioned battery types.

Table 2: Summary of the potential magnitude of energy density and power density for the mentioned battery types.

	Lithium-ion Batteries	Beyond Lithium-ion (Conversion Electrodes):	Beyond Lithium-ion (Insertion Electrodes):	All-Solid Batteries	Flow Batteries:
Energy Density	150 Wh/kg to 250 Wh/kg.	300 Wh/kg to 500 Wh/kg.	150 Wh/kg to 300 Wh/kg	200 Wh/kg to 400 Wh/kg.	20 Wh/kg to 100 Wh/kg.
Power Density	500 W/kg to 2000 W/kg.	100 W/kg to 500 W/kg	200 W/kg to 1000 W/kg	100 W/kg to 500 W/kg.	10 W/kg to 100 W/kg.

The maximum travel distance and weight supported by each battery type can vary depending on various factors, including the specific aircraft design, efficiency, power requirements, and other operational considerations. However, Table 3 provides a general indication of the weight and maximum travel distance based on the energy density of each battery type.

Table 3: Summary of the potential magnitude of energy density and power density for the mentioned battery types.

	Lithium-ion Batteries	Beyond Lithium-ion (Conversion Electrodes):	Beyond Lithium-ion (Insertion Electrodes):	All-Solid Batteries	Flow Batteries:
Weight Support	Good balance between energy density and power density. Suitable for various sizes of electric aircraft.	High energy density. Suitable for larger electric aircraft with higher power demands.	Good balance between energy density and power density. Suitable for various aircraft sizes and power requirements.	High energy density. Support larger aircraft with	Relatively lower energy density can limit their weight support capability. Suitable for smaller electric aircraft with lower power demands.
Maximum Travel Distance	From hundreds to a few thousand kilometers.	From hundreds to a few thousand kilometers	From hundreds to a few thousand kilometers	From hundreds to a few thousand kilometers	Shorter travel distances, from tens to a few hundred kilometers.

4.3. Other aspects.

This section discusses in more detail some of the relevant issues such as safety challenges, fast charging challenges, overall lifespan, maintenance, battery packs, raw materials, manufacturing and disposal and TRL level.

	Lithium-ion Batteries	Beyond Lithium-ion (Conversion Electrodes):	Beyond Lithium-ion (Insertion Electrodes):	All-Solid Batteries	Flow Batteries:
Safety challenges	Thermal runaway. Flammable electrolytes. Dendrite growth.	Complex chemical. Electrolyte Incompatibility. Capacity Fade and Cycle Life.	Electrode instability. Flammable or volatile. Limited understanding.	Internal short circuits. Thermal management. Manufacturing Quality Control.	Electrolyte Leakage. Chemical Compatibility. Fire and Thermal Runaway.
Fast charging challenges	Limited Ion Mobility. Electrolyte Imbalance.	Reaction Kinetics. Electrode Stability.	Diffusion Kinetics. Electrode Degradation.	Ion Diffusion Limitations. Interfacial Resistance.	Limited Ion Mobility. Electrolyte Imbalance.
Overall lifespan	Capacity Fade. Lithium Plating and Dendrite Formation.	Electrode Stability. Electrolyte Incompatibility.	Electrode Degradation. Side Reactions.	Interface Stability. Volume Changes.	Electrolyte Degradation. Electrode Fouling.
Maintenance	Well-established maintenance practices. Regular monitoring of cell health, managing operating conditions (temperature, voltage, current), and implementing battery management systems (BMS). Issues related to cell aging, state of charge management, and electrode degradation may require additional maintenance measures.	May require practices similar to traditional lithium-ion batteries. Challenges relate to managing electrode stability, addressing capacity fade, ensuring compatibility between electrode and electrolyte materials, and optimizing thermal management systems.	Potential similar requirements to traditional lithium-ion batteries. Limitations include managing electrode degradation, monitoring and preventing capacity fade, addressing thermal management issues, and mitigating safety risks associated with fast charging and high-energy applications.	Potential for reduced maintenance requirements. May require periodic monitor the condition of electrode interfaces, assess solid electrolyte stability, and ensure adequate thermal management. Issues such as material degradation, electrode-electrolyte compatibility, and electrode-electrolyte interfacial resistance impact long-term maintenance requirements.	Potential for relatively low maintenance requirements. Still require regular maintenance to monitor and maintain electrolyte levels, check for electrode fouling, and ensure the proper functioning of pumps, valves, and other components. The complexity of the system and the need for large-scale installations pose challenges for maintenance in smaller, more mobile applications such as aviation.
Battery packs	Versatile and widely used in battery pack designs. Offer a high level of maturity and can be integrated into various configurations, allowing for flexibility in pack design and application-specific requirements.	Allowing for compact and high-performance battery packs. Can be integrated into battery packs using similar interconnection and packaging techniques as lithium-ion batteries.	Suitable for compact and high-power battery packs. Can be integrated into battery packs with existing lithium-ion battery pack designs, utilizing similar packaging and interconnection techniques.	Potential for compact and lightweight battery pack designs, due to their solid-state nature, with minimal additional components. Higher energy density and improved packaging efficiency.	Possibility of scalability and flexibility in designing battery packs due to their modular design. They can be easily scaled by adjusting the size of the electrolyte storage tanks and increasing the number of cell stacks.

Raw materials	Well-established raw material supply chains (lithium, cobalt, nickel, and graphite). State of the art involve optimizing material usage, recycling processes, and exploring alternative electrode compositions to reduce reliance on scarce materials like cobalt. Limited availability and potential geopolitical concerns (for cobalt). Diversify raw material sources, recycling and reduce cobalt dependency.	Offer possibilities to explore alternative materials more abundant and widely available, as sulfur, silicon, and metal oxides. Limited availability of certain raw materials, such as high-purity silicon. Additionally, addressing the stability and cycling performance of these materials remains an area of active research.	Leverage materials, which are relatively abundant and widely available, such as lithium cobalt oxide, lithium iron phosphate, and lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide. Research efforts aim to enhance energy density, cycle life, and stability. Limited availability of some raw materials, such as cobalt. Developing alternative electrode materials is an active area of research.	Can potentially use a variety of materials that are more abundant and widely available, for example, ceramics or polymer electrolytes. State of the art involve material synthesis and optimization to improve ion conductivity, stability, and compatibility. Additionally, the development of sustainable and eco-friendly electrode materials is an ongoing research area.	Primarily use vanadium-based electrolytes, which are commercially available. Wide range of electroactive materials, including abundant elements such as vanadium and iron. Research efforts focus on improving electrode materials and exploring alternative electrolytes to enhance performance and reduce costs.
Manufacturing and disposal	Well-established manufacturing processes and a mature supply chain. Challenges include maintaining electrode material quality, controlling electrode coating thickness, and ensuring proper electrolyte filling. Disposal requires adherence to recycling and waste management regulations due to environmental concerns associated with their materials.	Manufacturing build upon the state of the art in lithium-ion battery manufacturing. Challenges include ensuring compatibility between electrode materials and electrolytes, controlling side reactions during cycling, and maintaining consistent conversion efficiency. Proper disposal and recycling methods are essential due to the presence of potentially hazardous materials.	Manufacturing build upon the state of the art in lithium-ion battery manufacturing. Challenges include ensuring precise control over electrode material deposition, minimizing defects, and addressing electrode instability or degradation during cycling. Proper disposal and recycling needed.	Potential for simplified manufacturing processes. Challenges include ensuring consistent and uniform solid electrolyte deposition, electrode-electrolyte interface compatibility, and minimizing defects or impurities during the manufacturing process. Additionally, the disposal of solid-state batteries may require special recycling.	Manufacturing processes have been developed for stationary energy storage applications. Limitations include the need for large-scale installations, complex system integration, and the potential for corrosion or degradation of cell components over time. Additionally, the disposal of the electrolyte solution requires careful handling due to its chemical composition.
TRL	TRL 6 to TRL 9	from TRL 3 to TRL 6	from TRL 3 to TRL 6	TRL 2 to TRL 4	from TRL 2 to TRL 5

5. Conclusion

Aviation electrification aims to replace fossil fuel-based propulsion systems with electric powertrains in aircraft to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and decrease dependence on fossil fuels. Batteries are a crucial component of aviation electrification, providing energy storage that powers electric aircraft. Batteries must have a high energy density to fly long distances while carrying a full payload, be lightweight, maintain high energy density, be compact and efficient, and have good temperature tolerance.

This paper addresses the main performance requirements batteries will have to comply with, classify batteries according to its chemistry and comparatively analyses the most relevant types of batteries for matching aviation needs.

The assessment considers energy density, power density, cycle life, safety, size & weight, charging time and cost, indication of the weight and maximum travel distance supported by each battery type, as well as detailed information on safety challenges, fast charging challenges, overall lifespan, maintenance, battery packs, raw materials, manufacturing and disposal and TRL level.

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